

Human Corps Planning: A First-order Computational Model

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ABSTRACT

Most computational models of planning developed within AI typically rely on complete and accurate knowledge of the initial situation and a well-defined goal in order to execute. These conditions differ markedly from planning problems frequently encountered by human planners; they must construct plans even when the goal is ill-defined and knowledge about the environment is incomplete and possibly inaccurate. The goal of the research reported here has been to identify a plausible first-order model which characterizes the high-level control cycle of expert human planners in the task of battlefield planning. Literature on the training of battlefield planning experts, interviews with expert planners, Army doctrine, and observations of planning activities of human experts were used to construct the model. The model is evaluated against a verbal protocol of a simulated corps maneuver-control planning exercise conducted at the U.S. Army War College.

INTRODUCTION

Most computational models of planning developed within AI require complete and accurate knowledge of the starting situation as well as a well-defined goal for their operation. In marked contrast, human planners often must create plans despite the fact that the goal is often ill-defined and knowledge about the world in which the plan is to be executed is incomplete and possibly inaccurate. Battlefield planning is a paradigmatic example of such a planning context. Consequently, the development of a model of how planning takes place within this domain represents a considerable challenge to our current computational understanding of planning.

The research reported here is directed at this challenge. The focus of this research is primarily descriptive. The goal is simply to try to identify a plausible high-level description of the basic control cycle that might characterize the observed planning activity of human experts in battlefield planning. The research has proceeded by observing the planning activities of human experts, reviewing the pedagogy associated with the training of human experts, and then partially specifying a first-order model of a planning strategy that is suggested by these observations and Army doctrine.

Next, the proposed model is evaluated by comparing its "predictions" concerning the types of planning activities and their ordering that should be observed against a protocol of the planning activities of human experts.

Battlefield planning is an activity carried out at a variety of communicating levels of the Army command hierarchy. A higher level communicates to a lower level a partial specification of: a problem to be solved; the resources available for use in solving that problem and; some guidance on how the problem is to be solved. At each level of the command and control hierarchy, several experts are involved in the planning process. Information and decisions may be completely shared within a level whereas only limited communication is possible between levels. The planning itself may take place over a matter of days and the resulting plan provides the basis for coordinating and controlling the activities of many agents over a protracted period of time. Although planning is distributed over many agents with a relatively low-bandwidth of communication between levels, common knowledge about doctrine and general principles of battle seem to compensate for this low band-width.

In this research we have focused on the maneuver-control planning activity that is carried out at what corresponds to the corps level within the Army's command hierarchy. Clearly, the nature of the planning carried out at any level is influenced by the overall structure of this command hierarchy. However, we will not attempt to characterize the planning process as it moves from one level of the command hierarchy to another.

A First-order Model for Corps-level Planning

In the typical AI planning model, the determination of which information about the planning situation is relevant to the plan is discovered as part of the planning process. Relevant information is developed and associated with a subproblem in three ways. First, and most typically, information defining the subproblem is inherited from the parent subproblem. This is simply the standard mode of subproblem definition provided by the method of problem reduction. Second, information may become available as a result of simulating the effects of planned actions which precede the current subproblem

[1]. Third, a subproblem may be further specified as a result of constraint propagation that occurs when another subproblem is further refined [2,3].

Although any of these mechanisms of subproblem specification may be used in battlefield planning, they are not sufficient. In battlefield planning the relevant information upon which to base the plan is only partially and indirectly specified. Consequently, battlefield planning requires the planner to explicitly develop the information needed to further the planning process. There is a sense in which this planning process provides a basis for recognizing the information required and thus focuses efforts at data retrieval, inference or further data collection. This interplay between planning and data development is probably not atypical of human planning in complex information-rich domains. It is of particular interest in the battlefield domain because the process is not simply one of data retrieval, but also one that can involve complex inference strategies initiated to support the planning effort.

From the point of view of planning, this raises the question of exactly how such processes of retrieval and inference might be incorporated into the basic control structure of a planner. There are two basic ways in which a process that further specifies the information associated with a subproblem might be invoked during the control cycle of a planning model. The first is "triggered" and the second is "predictive."

In the triggered case, a subproblem is chosen and failure to identify any applicable reduction rule to decompose the subproblem provides a basis for recognizing that further information must be acquired. Here a failed rule of decomposition could provide the basis for determining what information is currently relevant to the derivation of a particular candidate solution. The interesting side-effect of this method of initiating a process of retrieval and inference is that the planning process itself can strongly bias the development of the information deemed relevant to the evolving plan.

In the predictive case, a subproblem is again chosen, but is evaluated to determine whether or not it is sufficiently formulated to support expansion prior to any attempt to decompose the subproblem. This latter model suggests that the planner possesses explicit meta-knowledge that supports both the recognition of when a subproblem is sufficiently formulated as well as knowledge about how to specify and solve the metaproblem of developing the information required to obtain a well-formulated subproblem. In this case, the planning bias is less likely to be introduced into the retrieval and inference process that has been initiated. This is because the problem of further specifying a subproblem is not initiated by a specific rule of decomposition, but rather by knowledge specified independently from the decomposition rules.

The triggered case is very similar to that used by a least commitment planner such as MOLGEN [2,3]. In this case the data searched is fixed, correct and complete.

The issue of bias does not arise. PLANX-10 [4,5] was also a planner that possessed powerful abilities to defer commitment and exercise arbitrary control over its order of expansion of subproblems; it also included the ability to draw default inferences when faced with an impasse due to incompleteness of its knowledge. However, the default inferencing strategy employed was limited and chaining of such inferences was not allowed. This tended to control the degree to which the resulting plan could be biased by the planning process itself as well as to provide the discipline required to simply annotate the ways in which the plan depended upon such default inferences.

Figure 1 graphically depicts the control cycle proposed for our first-order model of corps planning. The cycle is initiated by the input of a problem to the planner represented as the problem state-pair [lo-Go]. lo consists of information concerning the problem's initial state and Go the goal state. This basic cycle is expressed as meta-problems for the planner. It's application yields an overall depth-first search strategy in the space of decompositions. It involves first choosing a subproblem, next providing a formulation of this subproblem if this is required, next decomposing the subproblem, which may be followed by critiquing and posting constraints, which may next lead to a process of local repair, and then the cycle begins again with the now expanded tree. Such control is basically similar to that described for the planning model that implements a method of least commitment except that the meta-level problem of formulating a subproblem has been added.

Figure 1. Meta-level Control

We will use this possible control strategy employed by experts in battlefield planning in two ways. First, the list of metaproblems: choosing and formulating a subproblem, decomposing the subproblem, critiquing and evaluating the resulting decomposition, and possible repair of the decomposition, is used to provide a presumably exhaustive taxonomy of possible tasks that the experts might carry out during the planning episode. Consequently, we will attempt to determine whether the protocol provides evidence of the experts

engaging in these tasks. Second, this model predicts a particular ordering in which these tasks should be carried out. Again, we can attempt to determine the degree to which the planning protocol provides evidence consistent with this ordering. Finally, the model represents an overall depth-first search strategy where alternatives should be specified quite locally as part of a backtracking strategy.

METHODS

The model was applied against a verbal protocol of the planning activities observed during a planning exercise at the U.S. Army War College at Carlisle Barracks, Pennsylvania (1986).

Simulated Planning Exercise

This video-taped exercise provided the planning data that are analyzed and discussed in the *RESULTS* section. The participants in this exercise were two members of the student body, each of colonel rank and with considerable experience in planning. During the exercise the players assumed the roles of corps commander and corps G3 (operations officer). While the exercise was artificial in that the detailed staff action supporting the planning process was not played, it did address key problem-solving elements of the process and mental processes of these planners as they considered these elements. These elements, or tasks, include the mission, terrain, and enemy force analyses, and courses-of-action generation phases of the military planning process [6,7].

Exercise Scenario This paragraph provides an overview of the problem the experts were asked to solve. The United States' 11th Corps, with principal subordinates including the 4th Armored Division, the 90th Infantry Division (Mechanized), the 80th Infantry Division (Mechanized), and the 14th Armored Cavalry Regiment, has been assigned to the NATO Middle Army Group (MIDAG). Although hostilities have not commenced, it is believed that enemy forces will attack NATO forces across the German border. MIDAG has disseminated the MIDAG operations plan (OPLAN) for the forthcoming operation. As a MIDAG subordinate, the US 11 corps has been assigned a mission and given responsibility for a terrain sector as part of that OPLAN [8].

RESULTS

The results are organized into two major sections. In the first section, we develop a functional categorization of the information characterizing problem states in this type of planning. In the second section the categorization is exemplified in the course of examining the descriptive adequacy of the model. This examination is performed by comparing statements made by the planners, and the ordering of those statements in the protocol, to the types and ordering of metaproblems specified by the model.

Functional Categorization

The categorization is based on whether the information defining problem states in this type of planning is given to planners in a form directly usable for planning purposes or whether the planners must derive the information they need. Table 1 presents this functional categorization based on whether the information is: always given to the planners (Given); available but usually must be sought by the planners (Retrievable) or; unavailable and must be developed by the planners (Must-Derive). This categorization is exemplified at many locations in the protocol but only a small sample of instances illustrating it can be presented here.

Table 1 also presents an organization of the information types (e.g., Maps of region) that are associated with descriptions of either the initial- or goal-state of subproblems. Our understanding is that the initial statement of the problem (i.e., lo-Go) will always include the information types shown in category Given, but that the planners' need to retrieve and/or derive information may occur at the time they are given an OPLAN (i.e., lo-Go) or at any other point in the planning process. The significant requirement for subproblem formulation in this type of planning is reflected by the types of information in Table 1 which typically are not given to the planners, but which must be retrieved or derived by them. Subsection *Examination of the Model* further evaluates this hypothesis by presenting a subset of those statements in the protocol which appear to represent instances of subproblem formulation.

Descriptive Adequacy of the Model

In this section the descriptive adequacy of the model is examined by comparing a sample of the planners' statements (and their ordering in the protocol) to the types and ordering of metaproblems shown in Figure 1 ([9] provides a detailed analysis of the entire protocol transcript). Figure 2 shows the way in which the planning activities of the experts are organized under our first-order model. Here the horizontal dimension depicts the metaproblems and the vertical dimension, labelled 1 through 3, represents the ordered recurrence through this control cycle of the model. The numbering of the subproblem state-pairs [Ij-Gj] reflect the plan tree. Protocol statements associated with each step are referenced by the numbers in braces { } and thus reflect a temporal ordering of the planners' statements as they were made during the planning exercise.

Examination of the Model A global examination of the model can be made by observing the relationship between the metaproblems specified by the model and the line numbers associated with the lines of the transcript indicating the occurrence of those metaproblems (see Figure 2). This relationship indicates there is a strong correspondence between the ordering of metaproblems specified by the model and the ordering of planning activities in the protocol related

Table 1. Categories of Information for Problem States, Ij-Gj, Initial and Goal

<u>Given</u>	<u>Retrievable</u>	<u>Must Derive</u>
Ij:		
Maps of region -1:50,000 -1:250,000 Terrain Overview - description of own area of influence	Terrain factor overlays - roadnets - go/slow-no/no-go	Terrainobjects - obstacles - avenues of approach - key terrain
Operational overlay providing C2 measures - own sector boundaries - coordinating points, FEBA, phase lines (all optional)		Operational overlay providing C2 meas. - coordinating pts. - FEBA - phase lines
Enemy force - task organization - overlay - capabilities & intentions	Enemy order of battle (OB)	Enemy force capabilities and intentions (based on corps' assessment)
Task Organization for - own Army Group (AG) - theatre - deploying forces	Friendly OB - status - strength - history ...	Friendly force capabilities
Task Allocation for - own AG and each corps in AG		
Scheme of Maneuver for own AG		
Support Priorities for own corps		
Gj:		
Specified tasks (i.e., goals)		Implied tasks
Specified constraints - temporal and spatial - operational		Implied constraints - temporal & spatial - operational
Purpose(s) of tasks - partially specified - incomplete set		Purpose(s) of tasks - further specified - more complete set
Ordering of tasks - partially specified		Ordering of Tasks - further specified
Commander's guidance - two echelons above corps inclusive		Commander's intent - two echelons above corps inclusive

to those metaproblems. Also note that there is evidence in the protocol supporting formulation of subproblems.

Presented next is a small sample of the results of examining the model in the form of descriptions of problem state-pairs associated with the Formulate metaproblem in the model. Associated with these state-pairs are interpretive statements we made about the planning activities observed, and statements from the protocol which serve as evidence for these interpretations. Comments between [] are our annotations. Planning began when the experts were given a description of the terrain, a terrain map, enemy force and operational overlays, the enemy force task

organization, the task organization for MIDAG, and an OPLAN. These sources provided the initial formulation of the planning problem.

After reviewing the OPLAN and information on the enemy and friendly forces and the environment, the planners engaged in various terrain and enemy analysis activities which served to further formulate the initial state (I₀) and mission analysis activities which served to further formulate the goal state (G₀). The results of these activities provide the further formulation of I₀-G₀ and are represented in row 1 of Figure 2 as part of I₀-G₀. Evidence of these activities is given below.

Io':

a. Identifying obstacles to enemy force. "This canal here which is as deep as the Mittleland canal. The Weser, the Leine [both rivers], right in here is marshy." {2-3}

b. Identifying avenues of approach of enemy force. "The real objective however is a deep objective back here across the Leine. Rapidly. They're going to want to bypass Hannover and all this built-up stuff over here [map]. If they go north they can't use the autobahn. If the bridges are dropped on the autobahn they've got three river crossings to make, marshy areas here [map]. I put them down through here [map]." {12-18}

c. Locating enemy force main attack. "The main attack will be coming across here [map]." {21-22}

d. Identifying enemy feint of main attack. "[points to map] Some of these [enemy units], perhaps six, will try to make it through to feint an attack." {19-20}

Go':

Evidence that Go had been further formulated was discovered when the planners answered questions the interviewers asked regarding the planners' understanding of the commander's intent; at this point in the session the protocol indicates that the planners already had selected a top-level decomposition (I01-G01 and I02-G02). So, the transcript line numbers associated with further formulation of Go reflect the point in the session when the planners answered the interviewer's question rather than the point in the session when the further formulation of Go actually occurred.

In analyzing the mission statement and commander's guidance they receive from MIDAG, the planners need to understand the commander's intent. They must understand the relationships between the activities/tasks given (explicitly and implicitly) to the corps and MIDAG's concept of the operation. The OPLAN directed the planners to "trade real estate for destruction of PACT military forces (preserve command while inflicting

Figure 2. Representation of the Protocol Organized Under the First-order Model

maximum damage)." The planners understood this statement to mean they should conduct a dynamic (rather than static) defense and to try to maintain unit integrity in preparation for their counter-attack. The following protocol statements appear to reflect these mission analysis activities.

"You've got no requirement to conduct a static defense, number 1." {198-199}

"Focus on destroying enemy forces and at the same time preserving your own forces." {202-203} "if we understand the commander's intent we can plan a lot smarter because his intent is ultimately for us to counter-attack. Knowing that, it all makes sense. You can't counter-attack with nothing." {205-208}

Alternative Planning

Also of note is the fact that the experts developed, at most, two alternative plans. The second plan they generated, which was a revision of the first plan, was the result of backtracking to a location in the plan tree where all of the first plan to that point was retained in the second plan (Figure 2, row 3). The plan tree was expanded from that location to complete the second plan. Thus, the planning observed supports an overall depth-first search strategy (and associated local plan repair). It should be noted that the first plan they began to construct was constrained by guidance, in the OPLAN they were given, in such a way that they generated a partial plan which was different from what they would have produced if guidance had not constrained them in the way that it did. The planners recognized the second plan was in violation of that guidance, but they generated it for purposes of the exercise.

CONCLUSIONS

The most striking aspect of the protocol for this planning problem is the interleaving of the task of subproblem formulation with the tasks of subproblem decomposition, plan critiquing and plan repair. Further, the evidence from the protocol is quite consistent with the ordering of these tasks as predicted from our first-order model.

Another characteristic of the planning process was that it was done in a temporally forward direction with respect to the ordering of battle types faced by the corps. The planners appeared to impose one constraint on the counter-attack subproblem very early in planning, but otherwise they planned for the defensive subproblem first. It may be that an offensive mission would show more reasoning in the backward direction related to less uncertainty about the initial and goal states.

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